

ATTITUDE TOWARD USING INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY READINESS: STUDY ON MANAGER OF VILLAGE-OWNED ENTERPRISES IN LANGSA CITY

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the effect of Optimism and Discomfort on Readiness to Apply ICT with innovativeness as a moderator. Research data were collected through questionnaires, using stratified random sampling. Respondents consisted of directors, secretaries, treasurers and managers of Gampong-Owned Enterprises in Langsa City. The results showed that innovation and optimism had a positive and significant effect on the readiness to apply ICT, while discomfort had no effect on the application of ICT. Innovativeness cannot moderate the effect of discomfort on ICT use, and innovativeness cannot moderate the effect of optimism on ICT adoption readiness.

Keywords: Optimism, Innovativeness, Discomfort, Application of ICT, BUMG

INTRODUCTION

The establishment and development of village-owned enterprises (BUMDes) is an important issue and policy in an effort to improve the community's economy, especially in rural areas, which receives guidance from the Regency and City Regional Governments in Indonesia. The operational and business activities of BUMDes cannot be separated from the development of information technology globally, especially information and communication technology (ICT), which has eliminated regional and distance boundaries, as well as time. Utilization of ICT by managers and customers of BUMDes and other micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) is a necessity, so that they can operate effectively, efficiently, and sustainably.

Environmental changes require a shift from traditional business activities to technology-based ones (Kuratko and Audretsch, 2013). The rapid development of ICT requires business actors to be more innovative and able to adapt to these developments, including small and medium-sized enterprises (Fillis, et al., 2004; Simmons et al., 2011), so as to increase competitiveness and profitability (Aragón-Sánchez and Sánchez-Martin, 2005). The application of ICT also has the potential to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of business processes, and change existing business models for the better (Chong, 2004).

Tob-Ogu, et al. (2018) found that SMEs using information technology can gradually increase their competitive advantage. However, the use of technology in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) remains relatively low (Zafar and Mustafa, 2017), due to low abilities, attitudes, and resources (Wolcott, 2008). According to Wolcott (2008), the decision to implement ICT in a

business entity is highly dependent on the social system and attitude of the business actor, where the smaller the business entity, the more difficult it is to implement ICT.

The low use of ICT also occurs in Village Owned Enterprises (BUMDes), which are business units owned, by the village government. The enactment of Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages and Government Regulation Number 43 of 2014 concerning the Implementation of Law Number 6 of 2014, explains that villages can establish BUMDes. The mandate of establishing BUMDes is intended to accommodate the economic activities of the community in the form of an institution or business entity that is managed professionally, independently, effectively and efficiently. BUMDes is an integral part of economic growth which has an important role in creating job opportunities for the village community. BUMDes if managed properly are expected to be able to make a significant contribution to improving the people's economy, which has an impact on increasing PADes.

Economic pressures require business actors to be able to adjust conditions by conducting exploration which can increase the potential for survival and growth of business entities (Kitching, et al., 2011). Daniel and Grimshaw (2002) and Tan, et al. (2010) suggested that the use of ICT is not an alternative choice but a necessity for future business success. The use of technology will have an impact on the socio-economic development of an area where the business activity takes place (Yunis, 2017).

The decision to implement ICT depends on the attitude of the owner/manager of a business entity (Pawson, 2012). Innovative managers will tend to adopt a new technology model, but these managers also consider the costs of adoption, the opportunities and threats that arise from implementing the ICT (Simmons, et al., 2008). Parasuraman and Colby (2001) explain that measuring technology readiness can be seen from four attitudes or personalities of prospective ICT users, namely: optimism (optimism), innovation (innovativeness), discomfort (discomfort), and insecurity (insecurity).

This study adopts the technology readiness model developed by Parasuraman (2000) for the context of BUMDes. Readiness to apply technology is defined as a tendency or desire to use new technology to complete various activities carried out by BUMDes. This is done to capture the openness of users (in this case BUMDes management) to decisions to use ICT and ICT aspects, so that the level of readiness of BUMDes managers can be assessed to accept the application of ICT.

Langsa City has 66 villages, which should have 66 BUMDes, but of those 66 villages only 30 have BUMDes (Source: Langsa City BPMG). However, ironically out of the 30 BUMDes, only a few BUMDes are active and the rest are experiencing suspended animation. According to the Head of BUMDes, the Langsa Village Community Empowerment Agency (BPMG) is that the BUMDes managers do not have creative ideas so they do not have market competitiveness, and the weak resources that master technology so they cannot connect the products produced by BUMDes with the market by using technology.

Chaffey et al (2009) conducted research related to digital marketing, there are several benefits, namely the opening of new sales opportunities that result in increased revenue from

customers, market expansion, cost reduction due to reduced time for customer service, printing costs and distribution of marketing communications. In addition there are also intangible benefits, namely a better corporate and brand image, faster and more responsive marketing communications (including public relations), improved customer service, identifying new partners with a better website and service for customers, and being able to obtain customer feedback about the products offered.

BUMDes are small organizations, consisting of 10 (ten) managers for each BUMDes, but small organizations can have an important contribution to the economy of a country (Diaz, 2010) if managed properly. To face environmental challenges, such as rapid technological evolution, globalization, and increasingly sophisticated competitors, it is hoped that BUMDes managers will be able to identify, pursue market opportunities and adapt to a dynamic environment by implementing ICT. This study aims to determine the effect of the attitude of BUMDes managers on the application of ICT.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Readiness of ICT Application

Optimism is a positive view of technology and the belief that technology offers users increased performance, flexibility and efficiency. The following statement describes an indicator of the optimism dimension: liking the idea of doing business via a computer because it is not restricted to regular working hours. The importance of perceived ease of use is supported by Bandura's (1982) findings regarding self-efficacy, which is defined as an assessment of how well an individual can perform the necessary actions to deal with prospective situations. Self-efficacy is similar to perceived ease of use, because the belief defined in self-efficacy is a proximal determinant of behavior. This theory distinguishes self-efficacy assessment from outcome assessment which is concerned with the extent to which an individual's behavior when successfully carrying out a given task.

Parasuraman and Colby (2014) developed a Technology Readiness Index (TRI) which can be used to measure individual beliefs and thoughts or attitudes in general about their decision to use technology. There are four dimensions used to measure the readiness of this technology, namely: optimism, innovative, discomfort, and insecurity. Two of the four dimensions, namely optimism and innovation, are the drivers of technological readiness (benefactors), while the other two, namely discomfort and insecurity, are inhibitors.

Zhu et al. (2003) said that a business that is run using information and communication technology will have the potential to change the organization, change the organizational structure, and change business processes significantly. In addition, businesses that implement ICT have an impact on relationships with customers, suppliers and other business partners. Fishbein, & Ajzen (2010) explain that individual attitudes, behaviors, social environment and intentions are necessary to adopt ICT.

H1: Optimism affects the application of ICT

The Effect of Discomfort on ICT Application Readiness

Discomfort is a lack of control over technology and feeling overwhelmed by not knowing how to use technology or distrust of technology and skepticism about its ability to work well. The following statements cause inconvenience: that technological systems are not designed to be used by ordinary people, and when providing a service describing technology, individuals feel as if they are being taken advantage of by someone who knows more about technology.

Rojas-Mendez, et al. (2017) found that demographic variables and education level had an effect on the adoption of new technology. Experience using ICT and processing capabilities are factors influencing ICT adoption. In addition to technical knowledge and competence (Chapman et al., 2000) said understanding of market opportunities and the ability to apply new technologies can increase competitive advantage (Venkatraman, 1994; Mullins et al., 2001; Tetteh and Burns, 2001). Palvia and Palvia (2000) suggest that the age and experience of the owner/CEO are the most important factors governing the success of ICT adoption.

H2: Inconvenience affects the application of ICT

Influence of Innovativeness on ICT Application Readiness

Innovation is the tendency to be at the forefront of adopting technology and developing creative ideas or thoughts about the benefits of using new technologies. The following statements describe indicators of the innovation dimension: Individuals can find high-tech products without help from others, and are at the forefront of adopting newly introduced technologies (Pasuraman, 2000). Gratton and Ghoshal (2005) state that managers have an important role in creating innovative changes in organizations. Innovation does cost a lot.

Technology Readiness (TR) is the tendency of a worker/manager to use new technology in their workplace. Competence of workers/managers becomes a competitive advantage of a business entity, so it can be ascertained that the business entity can enter global competition and can support its organization to create new strategies about possible future technological developments now and in the future (Parasuraman, 2000).

H3: Innovativeness affects the application of ICT

Innovativeness Moderates the Effect of Optimism on the Implementation of ICT

Parasuraman and Colby (2001), and Colby (2002), classify five types of individual attitudes based on their level of technology readiness. The five types are: Explorer, pioneer/forerunner, skeptic, paranoid, and sluggish. The first group to adopt technology were explorers, who were highly motivated to adopt technology fearlessly. Pioneers are groups who want the benefits of a new technology but consider the difficulties and dangers. Skeptics are the group who need to be convinced of the benefits of new technology, and Paranoids, who are very considerate of the risks and are afraid to adopt new technology. The last, slow group is the

group that adopts technology because they are forced to do so (Parasuraman and Colby 2001).

Parasuraman (2000) found that although people are generally optimistic about the application of technology, there is still a lot of insecurity and even technology innovators experience anxiety as a result of the new technology they adopt. Ironically, although adoption of new technologies is increasing, surveys show signs of increasing consumer disillusionment with technology use.

H4: Innovativeness can moderate the Effect of Optimism on the Implementation of ICT

Innovativeness Moderates the Effect of Inconvenience on the Application of ICT

Discomfort towards new technology can be due to a tendency not to want to get out of the comfort zone or being afraid to face new things (resistance to change). Life experience and perspective on a problem can make a person change to be more creative and innovative. Therefore, too long in a comfort zone or position without any serious problems that have been enjoyed so far, can make a person lazy to change.

ICT is an important factor that drives innovation and performance of a business entity (Ramadani et al., 2016). Several previous studies examined the differences in individual attitudes in the application of new technology (Harrison and Rainer 1992). There are many variables that differ in individual attitudes, including demographics (Zmud 1979). Gender, age, experience, and personality, and computer skills (Harrison and Rainer, 1992).

The benefits of using ICT are an important concept in technology acceptance, which can be an indicator of the extent to which the use of technology can increase the effectiveness of the business activities of technology adopters (Irani et al., 2009). Pagani (2004) asserts that the benefit of using ICT is one's belief that a particular technology can be considered for adoption to improve performance. In the context of marketing, the value of technology is reflected in the costs incurred for implementing ICT compared to the benefits to be received. The higher the value of an ICT, the more attractive it is to implement. On the other hand, the perceived low value of ICT will be an obstacle for entrepreneurs to apply the technology.

H5: Innovativeness can moderate the effect of discomfort on the application of ICT

METHOD APPROACH

This study examines the effect of two independent variables, namely Optimism and Discomfort, on the dependent variable, namely the application of ICT, with one moderating variable, namely innovative. Optimism variable is defined as the extent to which individuals believe that technology can be beneficial to their lives and provide many benefits such as flexibility, and efficiency; and a desire to experiment with new technologies. The structural model in this study has reflective indicators. Which is a manifestation of the construct and is in accordance with classical test theory which assumes that the variance in the measurement of the latent variable score is a function of the true score plus the error (Ghozali, 2015).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

1. Characteristics of Research Respondents

Characteristics of respondents provide an overview of respondents from the selected sample. Characteristics of respondents are classified based on gender, education level, age, and position. Characteristics of respondents based on the gender of male respondents as much as 75.8% and female respondents as much as 24.1% of the 124 respondents. Characteristics of respondents based on age shows that the majority of respondents are in the age of 40-45 years. Meanwhile, for the characteristics of education, it can be seen that the majority of respondents have a high school education level (SMA). The characteristics of the position of the majority of respondents have a position as director of BUMDes.

2. Preliminary Research Model Results

The path analysis model for all latent variables in PLS consists of three tests, namely: Inner model, which specifies the relationship between latent variables (structural model), outer model, which specifies the relationship between latent variables and their indicators or manifest variables (measurement model), and weight relations. , which is used to assess cases of latent variables and indicator/manifest variables on a zero means and unit variance scale (standardized values), so that location parameters (constant parameters) can be omitted in the model (Ghozali, 2014:37).

The data is processed using SmartPLS software with the model executed using the PLS Algorithm and Bootstrapping. The initial model image obtained with complete variables and indicators can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 1: Early Research Model

The results of the outer model show that not all indicators have an outer loading value above > 0.50 , which means that not all indicators meet convergent validity or are valid. Some indicators that do not meet the criteria for the Optimism variable indicator are X1.4, X1.5, X1.6, and X1.10. The Discomfort variable indicator is X2.3. Innovative variable indicator (moderating) is M1.1 and IT Implementation variable indicator is Y1.3. All indicators that were not valid for measuring the construct were removed or excluded from further testing.

3. Advanced Testing Model

Further testing is carried out by first removing the indicators that do not meet the requirements (invalid) based on the initial research model. The advanced model can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 2: Advanced Research Model

4. Measurement Model Testing (Outer model)

This test includes construct validity testing (convergent and discriminant) and internal consistency testing. The construct validity test using the PLS algorithm produces the outer loading value of each indicator on the construct. Outer loading whose value is below 0.50 will be dropped from the analysis because it has a low convergent validity value. The outer loading value of each indicator can be seen in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Outer Loading

Indicator	X1	X2	Y1	M1
X1.1	0.820			
X1.2	0.832			
X1.3	0.764			
X1.10	0.798			
X2.1		0.706		
X2.2		0.611		
X2.4		-0.646		
X2.5		0.507		
X2.6		0.680		
Y1.1			0.815	
Y1.2			0.850	
Y1.4			0.859	
M1.2				0.938
M1.3				-0.596

Source:Results of data processing with SmartPLS (2020)

Then, discriminant validity testing is carried out to ensure that each indicator has become a good comparison for the latent variables. The discriminant validity value is obtained by looking at the value of the square root of the AVE which is greater than 0.50.

Table 2: Discriminant Validity Test

Construction	AVE
Optimism	0.785
Inconveniences	0.634
Innovative	0.786
IT Application	0.842
Moderating Effect MX1	1,000
Moderating Effect MX2	1,000

Source:Results of data processing with SmartPLS (2020)

The construct reliability test was measured by two criteria, namely composite reliability and Cronbach alpha from the indicator block that measured the construct. The construct is

declared reliable if the composite reliability and Cronbach alpha are above 0.60 (Ghozali, 2015).

Table 3: Reliability Test

Construct	Composite Reliability	Cronbach Alpha
Optimism	0.889	0.843
Inconveniences	0.536	0.606
Innovative	0.132	-0.778
IT Application	0.879	0.794
Moderating Effect MX1	1,000	1,000
Moderating Effect MX2	1,000	1,000

Source: Results of data processing with SmartPLS (2020)

The output results of composite reliability and Cronbach alpha construct Optimism, Discomfort, and IT Application have a value above 0.60, so it can be said that the construct has good reliability. Constructs that have good reliability can be used to measure variables. Only the Innovative construct (as a moderating variable in this study) has a value below 0.60.

5. Structural Model Testing (Inner model)

Structural model testing is carried out using R-Square (R²) for the dependent construct, with the criteria that the R² value of 0.67 is good, the value of 0.33 is moderate, and the value of 0.19 is weak. Table 5 shows the R-Square and R-Square Adjusted values obtained in this study.

Table 4: Value of R-Square and R Square Adjusted

Dependent Latent Variable	R-Square	R Square Adjusted
IT Application	0.642	0.627

Source: Results of data processing with SmartPLS (2020)

The results of the data processing show that the R² value obtained is 0.642. This means that the model used can explain the effect of the Optimism variable (X₁) and the Discomfort (X₂) variable on IT implementation by 64.2%, while the rest (35.8%) is explained by other variables outside the model used.

Table 5 below presents the results of data processing to determine whether the hypothesis is rejected or cannot be rejected based on the structural model. The basis for the assessment is if the probability (P-Value) > 0.05 or t-count < t-table, then H0 cannot be rejected. If the P-value < 0.05 or t-count > t-table, then H0 is rejected. The magnitude of the t-table value for the level of significance or = 0.05 is 1.96 and the t-table for = 0.10 is 1.65.

Table 5: Inter-Variable Test Results and Significance Test

	T-Statistics	P-Values	Significance
Optimism→Application of ICT	6,480	0.000	Significant
Inconveniences→Application of ICT	0.693	0.489	Not significant
Innovative→Application of ICT	3,427	0.001	Significant
Moderation optimism→Application of ICT	0.925	0.355	Not significant
Discomfort of moderation→Application of ICT	0.053	0.958	Not significant

Source: Results of data processing with SmartPLS (2020)

Based on Table 5, the results show that of the five causal relationships or hypotheses that were built, only two relationships were statistically significant. That is, there are two null hypotheses that are rejected, namely the effect of Optimism on the application of ICT and the influence of Innovativeness on the application of ICT. Meanwhile, the null hypothesis which states that the effect of Discomfort on the Application of ICT, Innovativeness on the relationship between Optimism and the Application of ICT, and the influence of Innovative on the relationship of Discomfort with the Application of ICT, cannot be rejected.

Discussion

Based on Table 5, it can be seen whether the hypothesis is rejected or not based on the structural model, the basis for the assessment is if the probability (prob value) > 0.05 or t-count < t-table, then H0 is not rejected. If the probability (prob value) < 0.05 or t-count > t-table, then H0 is rejected. (T-table for = 0.05 is 1.96 and t-table for = 0.10 is 1.65)

1. The Effect of Optimism on the Implementation of ICT

Table 5 presents the results of data processing which shows that the t-statistic value for the Optimism variable is 6.480, greater than 1.96 (limited significance of influence with the assumption of 5% error tolerance). That is, statistically, the Optimism variable has a significant (significant) effect on the application of ICT.

The effect of optimism on the application of information technology has previously been theorized by Davis (1989). Davis (1989) stated that attitude is an antecedent to the intention to adopt technology. Meuter, et al. (2003) found that technology anxiety is defined as a user's

state of mind about his ability and willingness to use technology-related tools. Bobbitt and Dabholkar (2001) found an individual's attitude towards the need to understand technology in general, not specifically.

Optimism statements in this study have a positive meaning about technology and its ability to transition, using ten statements in the questionnaire. On average, respondents answered strongly agree, which means that the attitude of the BUMDes managers is very high towards the application of technology.

2. The Effect of Inconvenience on the Application of ICT

The t-statistic value for the Discomfort variable was 0.693 (see Table 5), less than 1.96. That is, statistically, the Discomfort variable has no effect (not significant) on the application of ICT.

Research Westjohn, et al. (2009) and Wang, et al. (2017) explained that new technologies offer great benefits to users, including increased comfort, control, and the freedom to act within limited space. All of these things are important factors in everyday life, thereby attracting potential users to use technology (Ali, et al., 2015). From the opposite perspective, some individuals, may not be psychologically prepared to decide to use technology, for example, the appearance of a service that is too sophisticated to cause discomfort to potential users (Lin and Hsieh, 2007), and the use of technology requires more effort to learn it (Bateson, 2007). 1985).

3. Influence of Innovativeness on IT Implementation

The results of data processing presented in Table 5 show that the t-statistic value is 3.427, greater than 1.96. This means that the Innovative variable has a positive and significant effect on the ICT Application variable.

ICT innovation and progress are urgently needed in the era of globalization (Linan, et al., 2019). Innovation is an individual's willingness to try something by utilizing thought, imagination ability, and various stimulants. Several studies on individual decision making show that individual choices are based on beliefs about the benefits received. Innovation is an activity that requires extensive communication. Surry and Farquhar (1997) stated that individuals who tend to be innovative will adopt an innovation earlier than those who are less. Innovators are risk takers and pioneers who adopt innovations.

The statement about Innovative in this study means that respondents have a tendency to be at the forefront of technological advances. This can be seen from the respondents generally answered agree with all Innovative statements, which means that BUMdes managers want to innovate on technological progress. In BUMDes, innovators can be identified as the most important part in adopting new technology; innovation is what is needed, to revive BUMDes that are "suspended in death". Khalil & Ezzat (2005) state that effective technology management can create wealth for organizations that have the ability to manage technology resources and assets effectively.

4. Innovativeness Moderates the Effect of Optimism on the Implementation of ICT

Based on Table 5, it can be seen that the t-statistic value for the Innovative variable is 0.925, smaller than 1.96, which means that Innovative cannot moderate the effect of Optimism on the Implementation of ICT. This shows that the Innovative attitude does not contribute to influencing the causal relationship between Optimism and ICT Application.

Attitudes towards innovation have been previously investigated by Rogers (1995). Rogers (1995) says that innovation decisions occur when individuals have the freedom to make decisions to adopt innovations that are independent of the social environment, while collective decisions occur when a group decides to adopt an innovation. The two decisions influence each other to decide to adopt an innovation or not, the adoption of this innovation is the root of the decision to implement a new technology.

Previous research on MSMEs explains that there is a time lag in terms of acceptance of innovation between innovators of large-scale business entities and small-scale business entities. The study explains that large-scale business actors are among the first to adopt an innovation, while small-scale business entities are among the lagging behind. Reasoned Action Theory/TRA (Fisbein and Ajzen, 2010) describes how innovation is an important part of the industry, TRA explains various elements that influence users' decisions to adopt and accept innovation. Users in this study are BUMDes managers, so differences in behavioral backgrounds originating from education, culture, knowledge, environmental influences, and personality play a role in the application of technology.

5. Innovative Moderates the Effect of Inconvenience on ICT Applications

The t-statistic value for the Innovative variable in moderating the effect of Discomfort on ICT Application is 0.053, smaller than 1.96. That is, the Innovative variable cannot moderate the effect of Inconvenience on the Application of ICT.

The perspective of innovation in communication developed by Rogers (1995) states that innovation is a communication model to understand the factors that affect the level of acceptance or rejection of acceptance of a thought/change. Innovation has several characteristics, which consist of: innovators, early adopters, groups that respond quickly to innovations but cannot influence others.

According to Rogers (1995), the majority are later adopting and those who are late adopting. The first group to adopt an innovation is innovators, who tend to be more educated, earn more, travel more, and read more. The second and third are groups that respond quickly to innovations but cannot influence others. And the majorities who later adapt innovations are groups that adopt as a result of norms and peer pressure. They are trend followers and are only motivated to adopt after others have. And the last to adopt innovative ideas are those who lack resources, especially the economy. They must be convinced that the innovation will not fail before they adopt the innovation.

CONCLUSION

Some conclusions that can be drawn from the results of this study are:

a. Optimism affects the Readiness of ICT Application

The BUMDes manager in Langsa City has a high level of optimism towards the application of ICT, but it must be balanced with increased skills in the form of training, so that the technology applied is in accordance with the needs and has an impact on improving the performance of BUMDes.

b. Inconvenience does not affect ICT Application Readiness

On average, BUMdes managers in Langsa City are still young, so they are more willing to take risks using technology without considering their abilities, prices, and the consequences they receive from using the technology.

c. Innovativeness affects the Readiness of ICT Application

BUMdes managers can accept innovations caused by environmental changes and technological advances. However, an analysis of conditions is needed to implement these innovations, including: level of knowledge and skills, availability of resources, availability of time, rewards/incentives, participation, commitment, and leadership.

d. Innovativeness cannot moderate the effect of Optimism on ICT Application Readiness

BUMDes managers in Langsa City, have different educational backgrounds, knowledge, and different environmental influences, so that they can influence the decision to accept a new technology.

e. Innovative cannot moderate the effect of Discomfort on ICT Application Readiness

BUMDes managers in Langsa City can be categorized as a group that responds quickly to innovation but is also the majority who later adapts innovations; this is due to the tendency to apply ICT only to follow trends.

f. This study has limitations because it only examines the readiness for adoption of the attitude of BUMDes managers, does not examine the attitude of consumers who use BUMDes services or products related to the application of new technology.

REFERENCES

- Ajzen, I., and Fishbein, M. 1977. Attitude-Behavior Relations: A Theoretical Analysis and Review of Empirical Research. *Psychological Bulletin*, 84: 888-918.
- Ali, B., Baluch, N. and Udin, Z.M. 2015. The moderating effect of religiosity on the relationship between technology readiness and diffusion of electronic commerce, *Modern Applied Science* 9(12): 52-60.
- Aragón-Sánchez, A. and Sanchez-Martin, G. 2005. Strategic orientation, management characteristics and performance: A study of Spanish SMEs. *Journal of Small Business Management* 43(3): 287-308.
- Barhoumi, Chokri. 2016. User acceptance of the e-information service as information resource: A new extension of the technology acceptance model. *New Library World* 117(9/10): 626-643.
- Bateson, J.E.G. 1985. Self-service consumer: an exploratory study. *Journal of Retailing* 61(3): 49-76.

- Beaver, G. 2007. The strategy payoff for small enterprises. *The Journal of Business Strategy*, 28(1), 11-17. doi: 10.1108/02756660710723161
- Bobbitt, L.M. and Dabholkar, P.A. 2001. Integrating attitudinal theories to understand and predict use of technology-based self-service. *International Journal of Service Industry Management* 12(5): 423-450.
- Chang, Jeffrey, & Barun Dasgupta. 2015. An Investigation of the Barriers to E-business Implementation in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises. *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology International Journal of Industrial and Systems Engineering* 9(1): 26-36.
- Chaffey, D., Ellis-Chadwick, F., Mayer, R., Johnston, K. 2009. *Internet marketing: strategy, implementation and practice*. Pearson Education
- Chapman, P., James-Moore, M., Szczygiel, M. and Thompson D., 2000, Building internet capabilities in SMEs, *Logistics Information Management*, 13(6), pp. 353-360.
- Chong, S. 2004. Electronic commerce adoption by small and medium sized enterprises in australia: An empirical study of influencing factors. Paper presented at the 12th European Conference on Information Systems, Turku, Finland, 14–16 June.
- Clousing, Don and Holmes, Maurice. 2010. Technology readiness. *Research Technology Management* 53(4): 52-59.
- Cressy, R. 2006. Why do most firms die young? *Small Business Economics*, 26, 103-116. doi: 10.1007/s11187-004-7813-9.
- Davis, F.D., Bagozzi, R.P., and Warshaw, P.R. 1989. User acceptance of computer technology: A comparison of two theoretical models. *Management Science* 35(8): 982-1003.
- Didonet, Simone Regina, Andrew Fearn, & Geoff Simmons. 2019. Determining the presence of a long-term/short-term dilemma for SMEs when adopting strategic orientation to improve performance. *International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship*: 1-21.
- Fillis, Ian, Ulf Johannson, & Beverly Wagner. 2004. Factors impacting on e-business adoption and development in the smaller firm. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research* 10(3): 178-191.
- Gratton, L., & Ghoshal, S. (2005). Beyond best practice. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 46, 49-57. Retrieved November 27, 2014, from ProQuest database.
- (GhozalidanLatan, 2015). Partial Least Square. Konsep, Teknik dan Aplikasi Menggunakan Program SmartPLS 3.0 untuk penelitian empiris. Undip.
- Hassan, Masood Ul, Zeeshan Iqbal, & Maimoona Malik. 2018. Exploring the role of technological developments and open innovation in the survival of SMEs: an empirical study of Pakistan. *Int. J. Business Forecasting and Marketing Intelligence* 4(1):64-86.
- Harrison, A. W. and R. K. Rainer Jr. (1992), "The Influence of Individual Differences on Skill in End-User Computing," *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 9 (1), 93- 111.
- Irani, Z., Dwivedi, Y.K. and Williams, M.D. (2009) 'Understanding consumer adoption of broadband: an extension of the technology acceptance model', *The Journal of the Operational Research Society*, Vol. 60, No. 10, pp.1322–1334, DOI: 10.1057/jors.2008.100.
- Jordan, Rochelle Shivon. 2018. *Social Media Marketing Strategies Used by Small Retail Businesses*. Dissertation. Walden University.
- José I. Rojas-Méndez A. Parasuraman Nicolas Papadopoulos. 2017. Demographics, attitudes, and technology readiness: A cross-cultural analysis and model validation. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning* 35(1): 18-39. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/MIP-08-2015-0163>

- Kuratko, D.F. and Audretsch, D.B. (2013). Clarifying the domains of corporate entrepreneurship. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal* 9(3): 323-335.
- Lin, J.-S.C. and Hsieh, P.-L. 2007. The influence of technology readiness on satisfaction and behavioral intentions toward self-service technologies. *Computers in Human Resources*, 23(3): 1597-1615.
- Liñán, Francisco, Justin Paul, & Alain Fayolle. 2019. SMEs and entrepreneurship in the era of globalization: advances and theoretical approaches. *Small Business Economics* 6(1): 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-019-00180-7>.
- Mahmudi, A. Aviv & Damayanti. 2019. Penerapan Teknologi Informasidan Pengembangan Manajemen BUMDes “Bangun Yuwana” Desa Sumberjo Kecamatan Rembang, Kabupaten Rembang. *Jurnal Pengabdian Vokasi* 1(3): 164-167.
- Mbuyisa, Busisiwe & Awie Leonard. 2016. The Role of ICT Use in SMEs towards Poverty Reduction: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of International Development*. DOI: 10.1002/jid.3258
- Meuter, M.L., Ostrom, A.L., Bitner, M.J. and Roundtree, R. 2003. The influence of technology anxiety on consumer use and experiences with self-service technologies. *Journal of Business Research* 56(11): 899-906.
- Pagani, M. (2004) ‘Determinants of adoption of third generation mobile multimedia services’, *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, Vol. 18, No. 3, pp.46–59, DOI: 10.1002/dir.20011.
- Parasuraman, A. 2000. Technology readiness index (TRI): A multiple-item scale to measure readiness to embrace new technologies. *Journal of Service Research* 2(4): 307-320.
- Parasuraman, A. and Colby, C.L. 2001. *Techno-Ready Marketing: How and Why Your Customers Adopt Technology*. New York: Free Press.
- Parasuraman, A. and Colby, C.L. 2014. An Updated and Streamlined Technology Readiness Index: TRI 2.0. *Journal of Service Research*: 1-16
- Palvia, P. and Palvia, S., 1999, An examination of the IT satisfaction of small business users, *Information and Management*, 35, pp. 127-137.
- Pemerintah Republik Indonesia. Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 6 Tahun 2014 tentang Desa.
- Potnis, Devendra Dilip & Theresa A. Pardo. 2011 Mapping the evolution of e-Readiness assessments. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy* 5(4): 345-363.
- Rogers, E.M. 1995. *Diffusion of Innovations*, 4th ed., New York: Free Press.
- Sani, Asrul & Ninuk Wiliani. 2019. Faktor Kesiapan dan Adopsi Teknologi Informasi dalam Konteks Teknologi Serta Lingkungan pada UMKM di Jakarta. *Jurnal Ilmu Pengetahuan dan Teknologi Komputer* 5(1): 49-56.
- Sani, Asrul, T.K.A Rahman, Agus Budiyantra, and Rouly Doharma. 2020. Measurement of readiness in IT adoption among SMEs manufacturing industry in Jakarta. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 1511: 1-9.
- Schilling, M.A. (2008). *Strategic Management of Technological Innovation*. 2nd ed. New York, McGraw & Hill.
- Simmons, G., Armstrong, G., and Durkin, M. 2011. An exploration of small business website optimization: Enablers, influencers and an assessment approach. *International Small Business Journal* 29(5): 534–561.
- Smith, M.B. 2006. A study on South African corporate business failures. *The Business Review*, 6(1), 168-172.
- Sperber, G. 2007. A business plan is a life plan. *California Journal of Oriental Medicine*, 18(1), 16.
- Surry, D. W., & Farquhar, J. D. 1997. Diffusion theory and instructional technology. *Journal of Instructional Science and Technology*, 2(1), 24-36.

- Tob-Ogu, A., Kumar, N. and Cullen, J. 2018. ICT adoption in road freight transport in Nigeria: A case study of the petroleum downstream sector. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 131: 240-252. DOI: 10.1016/j.techfore.2017.09.021.
- Tsikriktsis, N. 2004. A technology readiness-based taxonomy of customers. *Journal of Service Research* 7(1): 42-52.
- Venkatesh, V., & Bala, H. 2008. Technology Acceptance Model 3 and a Research Agenda on Interventions. *Journal Compilation 2008*, Decision Sciences Institute.
- Wang, Ying, Kevin Kam Fung So, and Beverley A. Sparks. 2017. Technology Readiness and Customer Satisfaction with Travel Technologies: A Cross-Country Investigation. *Journal of Travel Research* 56(5) 563-577.
- Westjohn, S., Arnold, M.J., Magnusson, P., Zdravkovic, S. and Zhou, J.X. 2009. Technology readiness and usage: a global-identity perspective. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science* 37(3): 250-265.
- Yunis, M., El-Kassar, A. and Tarhini, A. 2017. Impact of ICT-based innovations on organizational performance: the role of corporate entrepreneurship. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management* 30(1): 122-141. DOI: 10.1108/JEIM-01-2016-0040.
- Zafar, A. and Mustafa, S. 2017. SMEs and its role in economic and socio-economic development of Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences* 7(4): 195-205. DOI: 10.6007/IJARAFMS/v7-i4/3484.
- Zmud, R. W. 1979, Individual differences and MIS success: A review of the empirical literature. *Management Science* 25 (10), 966-79.